

pH and Sorption of Anionic Dyes by Alumina and Their Column Chromatography. Part V

G. L. MUNDHARA, M. P. TIWARI,

Department of Chemistry, Govt. College of Science, Raipur (M.P.)

and

J. S. TIWARI*

Department of Chemistry, Govt. Girls' College, Raipur (M.P.), 492 001, India

Manuscript received 24 November 1979, accepted 22 December 1979

The adsorption-desorption behaviour of HCl-treated chromatographic alumina of varying surface pH (pH 3.5-8.6) with aq. solutions of anionic dyes, orange II (OG) and naphthol blue-black (NB), under a variety of conditions of time, temperature and concentration, has been investigated. The adsorption is found to be pH-dependent. The greater degree of adsorption in short time-interval (10-30 min), low values of heat of adsorption (-3 to -11 kcal/mole), and easy desorption with inorganic anions have been interpreted by ion-exchange mechanism. The two dyes have been separated on alumina column.

In continuation of our study¹⁻³, two anionic dyes, orange II and naphthol blue-black, were taken-up to investigate their adsorption-desorption behaviour on alumina of pH 3.5-8.6. The results were used in their column chromatography. pH of alumina means its surface pH.

Experimental

Substrate :

Alumina samples of pH 3.5 to 8.0 were prepared by treating basic Brockmann alumina (pH 8.6) with varying concentrations of HCl-acid or water, as described earlier¹.

Solutes :

Orange II (C. I. No 15510) was prepared in the laboratory (sulphanilic acid → 2-naphthol). Naphthol blue-black (Michrome No. 1113) was the Merck sample (Fig. 1). They were recrystallised thrice from ethanol: water (1:1, v/v), and dried at 80° for 24 hr. The homogeneity of the samples was tested chromatographically.

Procedure :

From the stock solution of the dyes (0.1 g/l) in water, 10-80 ml solutions were withdrawn, diluted to 100 ml, and estimated colorimetrically at 485 nm (OG) and 620 nm (NB) respectively⁴. Spekol spectrophotometer (Carl Zeiss, accuracy ± 0.5%)

* Senior Author.

Orange II — C₁₆H₁₁N₂O₄SNa

Molecular weight — 350

Naphthol blue-black — C₂₂H₁₄N₆O₉S₂Na₂

Molecular weight — 617

Fig. 1. Structure of orange II and Naphthol blue-black.

was used for the estimations. The absorbance of the dyes was not affected by change in pH (pH 3.5-8.0). However, OG changes its colour at pH ≥ 8.0 which could be restored by the addition of sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer (pH 4.5).

Adsorption experiments were conducted by equilibrating alumina (0.25 g) with the dye solutions of known concentration in 25 ml-volumetric flasks. The flasks were immersed in thermostat, and periodical shaking was made. After a specified period, 2 ml of the aliquot withdrawn, centrifuged and estimated.

Adsorption vs Time and Temperature :

The variation of adsorption as a function of time (10 min-24 hr) was studied with alumina of pH 3.5-8.0 at $30 \pm 1^\circ$. The dyes show fast adsorption. Quantitative adsorption of OG occurred in 10 min (pH 3.5-5.0) and NB required 30 min for complete adsorption (pH 3.5-6.0). At higher pH, the equilibrium is almost attained in 1 hr (OG) and 4 hr (NB).

The temperature-effect studies (30° - 60°) show the process to be exothermic (pH 3.5-8.0), and the isosteric heats of adsorption is calculated to be -5 to -11 k cal/mole (OG) and -3 to -5 k cal/mole (NB). Graphs and data are not shown.

Adsorption vs pH :

The results of change in the nature of adsorption with pH are shown in Figs 2 and 3. It is observed that the affinity of the solutes gradually increases with decrease in pH of the substrates. Quantitative adsorption occurs at pH 3.5-6.0 (NB) and pH 3.5-5.0(OG). The process drops to zero at pH of 8.0(OG) and 8.6 (NB). The isotherms are of L_2 -type, not having a well-defined plateau, probably because of very low dye-concentrations used in the study.

Desorption Studies :

The degree of reversibility of sorption of the dyes (pH 3.5-8.0, 24 hr, $30 \pm 1^\circ$) was tested with a number of organic solvent-water mixtures and aq. inorganic electrolytes (M/100 NaCl, Na_2SO_4 , Na_3PO_4) as described earlier¹.

Fig 3 Adsorption isotherms of naphthol blue-black from aqueous solution on alumina of varying pH

The study reveals that the dyes are completely desorbed with pyridine-water (1 : 4, v/v), ethanol : *n*-butanol : buffer of the corresponding pH (1 : 1 : 2) and aq. Na_2SO_4 . Sodium chloride also desorbs the dyes effectively (Table 1).

TABLE 1—DESORPTION OF OG AND NB WITH aq. NaCl
Initial concentration, 80 mg/l

Dyes	pH of alumina samples and % desorption					
pH	4.0	5.0	6.0	6.5	7.0	7.5
OG	40	60	75	90	100	100
NB	28	42	50	62	90	100

Quantitative desorption takes place with aq. Na_2SO_4 and Na_3PO_4 (M/100).

Fig 2 Adsorption isotherms of orange II from aqueous solution on alumina of varying pH

Results and Discussion

The dyes investigated are the sodium salts of sulphonated aromatic compounds, such as Na^+D^- . The acid-treated alumina may adsorb these anionic dyes by ion-exchange of single dye-anions or aggregated dye-anions (micelles) or through covalent bond formation with the anionic groups (e.g., sulphonate) of the dyes.

The ion-exchange is shown by :

- (i) The greater degree of adsorption in a short time-interval, and low values of heat of adsorption.
- (ii) *Reversibility of Adsorption :*

The desorption characteristics with inorganic electrolytes indicate ion-exchange nature of the process. The inorganic anions, it appears,

probably compete with the dye-anions at the film surface for the ionic sites. In the presence of these desorbents (1 ml, *M*/100 solution), adsorption of the dyes is retarded considerably, and in contact with PO_4^{3-} ions, it does not occur. It is likely that at low *pH*, a primary reaction of the type shown below may occur :

Potentiometric titration results of the Cl^- ions released after adsorption of the dyes show an increase in the concentration of the ions at $\text{pH} \leq 6.0$.

Desorption with pyridine-water is rather difficult to explain at this stage. Certain studies⁵ suggest disaggregation of dyes in the presence of basic substances like pyridine, urea, dimethyl formamide, which form an adduct or complex.

(iii) *pH and Adsorption :*

The ionically-bound chloride content of alumina appears to decrease continuously with increasing *pH*, becoming essentially negligible in basic range. It appears that rapid exchange of the dye anions occurs at $\text{pH} \leq 5.0$ (OG) and $\text{pH} \leq 6.0$ (NB), followed by a slow exchange at sites within the alumina. The slow inward diffusion into the micropores of the substrates at higher *pH* may cause somewhat longer equilibrium period.

At high *pH* values, the H^+ ions of the $\text{>Al}-\text{OH}$ of the substrates tend to dissociate from the oxygen, leaving negative charge on the surface. As the *pH* is lowered, additional $-\text{H}^+$ may associate with the $-\text{OH}^-$, leaving a net positive charge, which will attract the dye-anions.

As the dye-anions are very large compared with the original ions (chloride ions), they may cover the surface with a mono-layer and screen off, to some extent, the surface forces which attracted the first layer. If screening is sufficiently good, a mono-layer will be irreversible adsorbed. This is also evident from the L_2 -type of isotherms.

It is observed that NB has a greater affinity for the substrates in comparison to OG. This observation is in accordance with Roosens' suggestion⁶ – greater the number of azo groups, the stronger is the adsorption. Also $-\text{OH}$ or $-\text{NH}_2$ is more effective in β -position of the naphthalene nucleus.

Thus, it appears that the adsorptive forces involved are predominantly coulombic (ion-exchange) and non-polar dispersion forces. The possibility of hydrogen bonding cannot be ruled out as free $-\text{OH}$ on the dye molecules may enter into this type of bonding.

Chromatographic Separation :

Synthetic mixtures of the two dyes were separated on alumina columns. Figs 2 and 3 reveal that OG and NB show about 70% and 90% adsorption respectively on alumina of *pH* 6.5. It has also been observed that buffer of *pH* 6.5 can completely desorb both the dyes. However, the rate of migration of the two dyes in the buffer mixed with ethanol and *n*-butanol (2 : 1 : 1, v/v) is different.

Method I : Quick-fit glass column (20 × 1 cm) was packed dry with alumina (20 g) of *pH* 6.5 to a column height of 12 cm. 5.0 ml each of the two dye-solutions in water (80 mg/l) were withdrawn, mixed, applied to the column, and kept as – such for an hour. On developing the chromatogram with 10 ml of buffer of *pH* 6.5 (potassium dihydrogen-phosphate : sodium hydroxide) containing ethanol and *n*-butanol (2 : 1 : 1), two distinct bands could be seen. Upper blue band of NB (0.5 cm width), colourless space (1.5 cm) followed by orange band of OG (1 cm). OG was eluted out of the column with 30 ml of the eluent.

The NB-zone could be desorbed on elution with 20 ml of ethanol : buffer of *pH* 6.5 (1 : 4, v/v).

Method II : The dyes OG and NB show 85% and cent-per cent adsorption respectively on alumina of *pH* 6.0 (Figs 2 and 3), and varying desorption with aq. NaCl (Table 1). These two observations, which lead to differential migration, have been applied for their separation.

The dye-mixture was added to the column (10 × 1 cm) packed with alumina (13 g) of *pH* 6.0 to a height of 8 cm, and kept for an hour. Aq. sodium chloride (*M*/100) was gradually added as eluting solvent. With 10 ml of the developer, two distinct bands, separated from each other (1.0 cm), were formed. OG was eluted out of the column with 30 ml of the eluent. The blue band of NB could be eluted out with 25 ml of aq. sodium sulphate (*M*/100).

The recoveries were quantitative.

The surface area of the alumina samples was determined to be 80-90 m^2/g (BET method). As the turning point in the adsorption isotherms is not well-defined, coverage factor (C.F.) could not be determined. However, if the relationship $-\text{C.F.} = 1.2 \times 10^{-7}$ (ionic weight)^{2,93} is considered⁶, the

C.F. of OG and NB is computed to be 2.8 and 14.3 respectively. It is observed that the dyes travel in the order of decreasing C.F.

References

1. G. L. MUNDHARA and J. S. TIWARI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, **55**, 1032.
2. G. L. MUNDHARA and J. S. TIWARI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, **56**, 737.
3. M. P. TIWARI, J. S. TIWARI and G. L. MUNDHARA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, **57**, 306.
4. E. GURR, "Synthetic Dyes in Biology, Medicine and Chemistry". Academic Press, 1971, p. 576.
5. C. H. GILES, A. P. D'SILVA and A. S. TRIVEDI, *J. Appl. Chem.* (London), 1970, **20**, 37.
6. L. ROOSENS, *Industrie Chim. Belge.*, 1952, **17**, 211.